

CONDENSATION OF ARSENIC CHLORIDE WITH DIALKYL AROMATIC AMINES.

BY PHULDEO SAHAY VARMA, K.S. VENKAT RAMAN
AND (MISS) K. M. YASHODA.

Arsenic trichloride has been condensed with methylethylaniline, dimethylnaphthylamine, dimethyl-*m*-toluidine and dimethyl-*p*-toluidine and the corresponding dialkylaminophenylarsenious oxides have been obtained. In the case of the first three compounds along with the arsenious oxides, tertiary arsenic compounds have also been obtained.

Arsenic trichloride condenses with dialkyl aromatic amines (Michelis and Rabinerson, *Annalen*, 1892, 270, 139) at the *para* position with respect to the tertiary amino group with the formation of *p*-dialkylaminophenylarsenious chlorides, which were isolated as the corresponding arsenious oxides. In the case of dimethylaniline, the reaction proceeds further, one molecule of arsenic trichloride reacting with three molecules of the tertiary amine forming a triarylsarsine compound {tri-*p*-dimethylaminophenylarsine, $[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4]_3\text{As}$ }. Later on, it was observed that the propyl ether of phenylmethylglycine and amylaniline in pyridine solution underwent similar condensation with arsenic trichloride.

In this paper the reaction of arsenic trichloride has been extended to a few more dialkylaromatic amino compounds. Methylethylaniline, dimethyl- α -naphthylamine, dimethyl-*m*-toluidine and dimethyl-*p*-toluidine condense with arsenic trichloride forming dialkylaminophenylarsenious oxides. The first three amines, methylethylaniline, dimethyl- α -naphthylamine and dimethyl-*m*-toluidine give along with arylarsenious chlorides, small quantities of the triarylsarsines as in the case of dimethylaniline, the arsenic group entering the *para* position with respect to the tertiary amino group and in the case of dimethyl-*p*-toluidine, where the *para* position is blocked, the condensation takes place in the *ortho* position.

The arsenious oxides have been converted into the corresponding chloride, bromide, iodide and arsenic acids.

The condensation of arsenic trichloride with methyl- and ethylbenzylanilines, dibenzylaniline and ethylbenzyl-*o*-toluidine does not proceed under similar conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Methylethylaminophenylarsenious Oxide, $(\text{EtMe})\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{AsO}$.—A mixture of methylethylaniline (15 g.) and arsenic chloride (25 g.) was

heated on a steam-bath for 2 hours. The resulting syrupy liquid was poured into cold water and the clear solution basified with sodium hydroxide solution (10 %) when some solid separated out which was removed. The filtrate was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the *p*-methylethylaminophenylarsenious oxide precipitated by the addition of an aqueous solution of sodium carbonate. The compound (13 g.) was purified by dissolving in dilute hydrochloric acid and reprecipitating by sodium carbonate. (Found: N, 6.32; As, 33.68. $C_9H_{12}ONAs$ requires N, 6.22; As, 33.33 per cent). It is a white powder, easily soluble in chloroform and hot alcohol and sparingly soluble in ether and benzene and easily soluble in both dilute alkali and acids, m.p. 74-75°.

The *sulphide*, $(EtMe \cdot N)C_6H_4AsS$, prepared by passing dry hydrogen sulphide into a solution of the oxide, is insoluble in water, easily soluble in chloroform, carbon disulphide and acetone. It had m.p. 157° after crystallisation from chloroform. (Found: S, 13.31. $C_9H_{12}NSAs$ requires S, 13.29 per cent).

The *chloride hydrochloride*, $(MeEt \cdot N)C_6H_4 \cdot AsCl_2 \cdot HCl$ is a white amorphous hygroscopic powder, easily soluble in water, alcohol, acetone and chloroform, m.p. 99°. (Found: Cl, 33.33. $C_9H_{13}NCl_3As$ requires Cl, 33.62 per cent). Sodium carbonate converts it into the oxide.

The *bromide hydrochloride*, $(MeEt \cdot N)C_6H_4 \cdot AsBr_2 \cdot HBr$ is a hygroscopic powder, m.p. 143°. It is easily soluble in water and practically insoluble in ether. (Found: Br, 54.1. $C_9H_{13}NBr_3As$ requires Br, 54.48 per cent).

The *iodide hydrochloride*, $(MeEt \cdot N)C_6H_4 \cdot AsI_2 \cdot HI$ is a light yellow powder decomposing on exposure.

p-Methylethylaminophenylarsinic acid, $(MeEt \cdot N)C_6H_4 \cdot AsO(OH)_2$, is a white amorphous powder, crystallisable from alcohol, and is soluble in chloroform, m.p. above 250°. (Found: As, 28.25. $C_9H_{14}O_3NAs$ requires As, 28.96 per cent).

Tri-p-methylethylaminophenylarsine, $[(MeEt \cdot N) \cdot C_6H_4]_3As$.— During the preparation of *p*-methylethylaminophenylarsenious oxide, the solids that separated on the addition of sodium hydroxide solution were treated with petroleum ether in which the unreacted amine dissolves leaving the triarylarsine 2.5 g. behind. These were washed repeatedly with petroleum ether and finally purified by crystallisation from chloroform, m.p. 206°. It is soluble in carbon disulphide and insoluble in ether, yield 2.5 g. (Found: As, 15.91. $C_{27}H_{36}N_3As$ requires As, 15.71 per cent). When equimolecular

quantities of methylethylaniline (5 g.) and arsenic trichloride (7 g.) were made to react, a better yield of triarylar sine (3 g.) was obtained.

1- *Dimethylaminonaphthyl - 4 - arsenious oxide*, $\text{Me}_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{AsO}$, was obtained by mixing together dimethylnaphthylamine (10 g.) and arsenic trichloride (26 g.) and warming on a water-bath for 1 hour and the arsenious oxide isolated as in the preceding case. The substance (7 g.) is a white amorphous powder, readily soluble in chloroform, hot alcohol and carbon tetrachloride and sparingly soluble in ether, m.p. $98-100^\circ$. (Found : As, 28.5. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{ONAs}$ requires As, 28.71 per cent).

The *sulphide* is a fine yellow powder, insoluble in water and easily soluble in chloroform, m.p. 144° . (Found : S, 11.54. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{NSAs}$ requires S, 11.58 per cent).

The *chloride* is very easily soluble in water, m.p. $110-12^\circ$. (Found : Cl, 28.99. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{NCl}_3\text{As}$ requires Cl, 30.21 per cent).

The *bromide* is a white amorphous powder, easily soluble in organic solvents except in ether. (Found : Br, 49.14. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{NAsBr}_3$ requires Br, 49.38 per cent).

The *iodide* is a pale yellow powder, m.p. $119-20^\circ$. (Found : I, 60.36. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{NI}_3\text{As}$ requires I, 60.75 per cent).

Tri- (1- dimethylaminonaphthyl) - 4-arsine, $[(\text{Me})_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6]_3\text{As}$. — The triarylar sine (2 g.) was formed along with the arsenious oxide and was isolated as in the previous case. It is a white amorphous substance, sparingly soluble in ether and very soluble in chloroform and carbon tetrachloride, m.p. 148° . (Found : As, 12.46. $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_3\text{As}$ requires As, 12.8 per cent).

4-*Dimethylamino-2-methylphenylarsenious oxide*, $(\text{Me}_2)_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{Me})\text{AsO}$, was obtained along with a little triarylar sine (1 g.) by mixing and warming on a water-bath dimethyl-*m*-toluidine (10 g.) and arsenic trichloride (25 g.) for 20 minutes, m.p. 108° . (Found : As, 33.09. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{ONAs}$ requires As, 33.33 per cent). The related *sulphide* had m.p. 137° .

4-*Dimethylamino-2-methylarsenic acid* does not melt below 250° . (Found : As, 28.71. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{NAs}$ requires As, 28.96 per cent):

Tri- 4 -dimethylamino- 2- methylphenylarsine, $[(\text{Me})_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{Me})]_3\text{As}$, is a white powder, soluble in chloroform and carbon disulphide, m.p. 98° . (Found : As, 15.58. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_3\text{As}$ requires As, 15.7 per cent).

2-Dimethylamino-5-methylphenylarsenious oxide, $(\text{Me})_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{Me})\text{AsO}$, was prepared by warming dimethyl-*p*-toluidine (10 g.) and arsenic trichloride (25 g.) on the steam-bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours, yield 4 g, m.p. $63-65^\circ$. (Found : As, 33.04. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{ONAs}$ requires As, 33.33 per cent).

Its *sulphide* had m.p. 68° . (Found : S, 13.32. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{NSAs}$ requires S, 12.29 per cent).

2-Dimethylamino-5-methylphenylarsinic acid, prepared in the usual way, is soluble in water. It does not melt below 250° . (Found : As, 28.69. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{NAs}$ requires As, 28.96 per cent).

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
BENARES HINDU UNIVERSITY.

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